

Smart city as a distributed platform: Toward a system for citizen-oriented management

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Abstract

Today's society must prioritize the design and development of platforms for Big Data processing. Smart cities generate large volumes of valuable data which the government can use to manage cities more intelligently. Aware of the value of data, many researchers have proposed architectures for optimized data collection and use. This paper proposes a novel approach that enables smart cities to reuse the functionalities of old applications by adapting them to new architectures. To be able to process large amounts of data and solve a variety of problems, smart city platforms need extra computing power. Two case studies have been conducted to verify the performance of the proposed platform. Those case studies have demonstrated that the development process of a smart platform can be simplified by implementing functionalities and components taken from earlier platforms.

Keywords: Smart cities, Internet of things, Distributed systems

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1. Introduction

Smart cities promote a sustainable lifestyle. Infrastructure, innovation and technology are the components that make smart cities efficient and self-sufficient. Examples of sustainability measures include the use of photovoltaic panels to provide electricity to buildings, street signs or electric vehicles. In addition, wind turbines are used to power street lights and the use of bicycles is encouraged as a means of moving around the city etc. The degree of sustainability of smart cities is measured according to a series of parameters, including: public management, social cohesion, governance, technology, urban planning, environment, mobility and transport, international projection, human capital and economy. Smart cities have got a huge variety of applications to monitor and control each of those parameters [1].

However, one of the barriers to efficiency is that different companies use different smart city applications to offer services to citizens. This can cause communication problems and can therefore hinder efficiency. Moreover, demand for new services is continuous in smart cities, so companies that wish to provide new services must make new developments instead of reusing and customizing the old ones. In addition, current smart city applications encounter major scalability problems due to the large amount of data they must process [2].

The problems described above evidence the importance of the solution proposed in this paper. The developed platform has a modular design which facilitates the efficient and transparent use of urban resources. Each module is responsible for the management and monitoring of a different element of a smart city. The platform interacts with both human beings and computers; it collects data autonomously and obtains data from users e.g. human interaction on social networks or third party data sources. Moreover, all the technology that has been used for its development is environment-friendly.

This platform has been designed to foster efficient habits among users through persuasive recommendations and collective challenges, leading to considerable changes in the behaviour of citizens and fostering efficiency in cities. Thanks to exhaustive data analyses, the platform may identify the specific needs of the different areas of a city, recommending the implementation of specific measures.

The platform is Cloud-based and it has a Big Data infrastructure that makes it capable of processing heterogeneous smart-city data coming from multiple sources. The data that flows into the platform is processed and

38 analyzed in order to generate personalized recommendations and motivate
39 citizens to develop efficient and environmentally friendly habits.

40 In addition, the platform must overcome a series of problems associated
41 with the large amount of heterogeneous data it collects. Smart city monitor-
42 ing and control platforms experience the following problems:

- 43 • Scalability; the needs and characteristics of a smart city change con-
44 tinually, existing platforms lack the ability to effectively adapt to those
45 changes. Monitoring and control platform must operate in a dynamic
46 environment, thus, the technology they use must be scalable.
- 47 • Reuse; the process of developing a new platform from scratch is very
48 time consuming and complex. Greater development efficiency must be
49 achieved through the reuse and customization of old functionalities in
50 new platform.

51 This research presents a novel platform that reuses software in order to
52 simplify the application development process. It has the capacity to process
53 the large volume of data generated by smart cities. In addition, its features
54 respond to the needs of today's smart cities; the platform is scalable which
55 means that it can adapt to the Internet of Things (IoT) or Industry 4.0
56 paradigms.

57 The platform has been designed under the paradigm of social computing
58 and is based on Kafka, a distributed streaming platform. Kafka Connect
59 and Apache Arrow enable communication between applications, scalability
60 and the reuse of software.

61 The purpose of the conducted case study has been to test the performance
62 of the proposed platform. A smart city model has been employed to simulate
63 the different situations and conditions that would normally occur in a real
64 smart city. This scenario addressed the problem of energy optimization in the
65 smart city. The platform has been used to manage and analyse the data of
66 the city, with the aim of optimizing energy consumption.

67 The case study made it possible to assess whether there is a change in
68 the citizens' energy consumption behavior and whether personalised, persua-
69 sive recommendations and collective challenges help maintain energy efficient
70 habits. Automatic learning techniques have been applied to heterogeneous
71 data (smart sensors, smart counters, social and public data) in order to
72 generate recommendations and challenges. Moreover, recommendations are
73 personalized through the segmentation of the target population according to

74 gender, socio-economic, demographic or cultural differences and through a
75 sociological analysis of the factors influencing consumer choices.

76 Furthermore, to test the platform in a real environment, the platform has
77 been connected to an intelligent control and automation system deployed in
78 homes/buildings. The platform obtained data from the system in order to
79 monitor consumption in real time and establish more efficient schedules while
80 maintaining a level of comfort.

81 A second case study has been conducted to show that the platform can
82 integrate multiple data sources of different nature; the data do not neces-
83 sarily have to come from sensors. In this case study, the platform has used
84 information retrieved from the Internet (social networks or websites obtained
85 in search results) to create profiles of real citizens. It has also been demon-
86 strated that the system can accept requests that involve large volumes of
87 information and take longer to process.

88 The main contribution can be summarized as follows:

- 89 1. The platform transforms the current understanding of client/server
90 communications. Its database has been converted into an interface;
91 this means that it is not necessary to have any knowledge about the
92 operation or programming of network communications when establish-
93 ing connections between various applications, and only a basic under-
94 standing of DB is required.
- 95 2. The abstraction layer allows to execute scripts for the reuse of modules.
- 96 3. Apache Arrow processes data and stores them in binary formats, facil-
97 itating faster data transfer.
- 98 4. The platform is symmetrical, this means that scalability can be achieved
99 easily, making it suitable for any project.

100 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related literature. The
101 proposed architecture is presented in Section 3. Then, Section 4 describes
102 the two case studies that have been conducted to validate the proposed archi-
103 tecture in both simulated and real scenarios. Finally, the conclusions drawn
104 from the results are presented in Section 5.

105 **2. Related work**

106 This section focuses on the current status of information management
107 platforms in smart cities. First, we review the current state of the smart city
108 concept and the work that is being carried out in this area, then we describe

109 the main smart city management platforms, and finally we identify the short-
110 comings of the platforms and propose possible solutions to be adopted in our
111 proposal.

112 *2.1. Smart City as the center of technological innovation*

113 In recent years, smart homes have been a broadly discussed topic in pol-
114 itics. ICT (Information and Communication Technology) infrastructure has
115 received considerable attention, although much of the research has also fo-
116 cused on the role of human capital/education, social and relational capital
117 and the environment; they have all been viewed as important drivers of ur-
118 ban growth [3]. The European Union (EU) has made a considerable effort to
119 develop a strategy for ‘smart’ urban growth in its metropolitan areas. The
120 Intelligent Community Forum conducts research on the local effects of ICTs
121 which are now available worldwide. The OECD (Oslo Manual and Euro-
122 stat, 2005) highlights the role of innovation in the ICT sector and provides
123 a set of tools for determining the coherence of innovation policies to shape
124 a sound framework of analysis for researchers on urban innovation [4]. At
125 the regional level, there has been renewed interest in soft communication
126 infrastructures and their effect on economic performance. There are sev-
127 eral applications that researchers are developing for a wide range of fields,
128 wireless sensors networks in smart cities [5] [6] or in agriculture [7],[8], en-
129 ergy optimization [9],[10],[11],[12], optimal resource allocation [13], risks and
130 challenges of adopting electric vehicles in smart cities [14], vehicular networks
131 [15],[16] and route optimization [17], [18], [19].

132 IoT is the very backbone of smart cities [20],[21]. IoT uses sensors to
133 collect and store data in the cloud for easy monitoring and control of smart
134 cities [22]. The city’s data can be used to effectively transform and manage
135 the city, and promote urban planning and development. To the best of
136 our knowledge, Big Data does not have a proper industrial definition, but
137 a survey shows that the key features of big data include high volume, high
138 velocity, and high variety.

139 A key feature of a Smart City architecture is its ability to acquire and
140 process data from multiple data sources (databases, crawlers, third-party
141 apps, sensors). Architectures require extra computing power to process large
142 volumes of data. The world of embedded systems has changed dramatically
143 over the last decade and its evolution is unlikely to slow down in the years
144 to come. Multicore processing (in the form of symmetric multiprocessing
145 (SMP) and asymmetric multiprocessing (AMP)) is becoming common, with

146 embedded multicore CPUs expected to grow by a factor of x^6 in the next years
147 (Venture Development Corporation). In addition, Field Programmable Gate
148 Arrays (FPGAs) have grown in capacity and decreased in cost, providing
149 the high-speed functionality that could only be achieved with Application
150 Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) [23]. Finally, virtualization is blurring
151 the connection between hardware and software by allowing multiple operating
152 systems to run on a single processor.

153 Through the aggregation of extra computing power we obtain an archi-
154 tecture with high-performance computing, capable of solving complex prob-
155 lems. To this end, the designed architecture relies on a distributed comput-
156 ing model which employs technologies such as clusters or agent-based parallel
157 computing. The majority of current distributed computing proposals involve
158 high-performance computing.

159 *2.2. Smart City platforms*

160 Nowadays there are multiple platforms whose functionalities promote the
161 IoT paradigm. These functionalities range from sensor networks to informa-
162 tion analysis, which involves information transmission, information fusion,
163 pre-processing, etc. The development of IoT platforms is a trend in the IT
164 sector which has resulted in the creation of numerous private/open and gen-
165 eral/specific platforms [24],[25],[26]. The most popular IoT platforms are
166 described below.

- 167 • FIWARE is a platform provides a series of APIs for the development
168 and deployment of Internet applications oriented towards multiple ver-
169 tical sectors. Many of those sectors are responsible for offering numer-
170 ous SC services.
- 171 • Carriots is a PaaS-type platform designated for IoT and M2M. It can be
172 used to connect the information-providing infrastructure to a SC. How-
173 ever, the platform remains at this level, without offering user-oriented
174 services, a layer that would have to be created independently of the
175 platform.
- 176 • Kaa is an initiative that defines an open and efficient cloud platform
177 to provide IoT solutions. Among the most common solutions is the
178 connection of all types of sensors that can be found or deployed in a
179 SC.

- 180 • Sofia2 is a middleware that enables interoperability between multiple
181 systems and devices, offering a semantic platform that makes real-world
182 information available to smart, mainly IoT-oriented applications.
- 183 • Webinos is a web application platform that allows developers to access
184 native resources through APIs. Webinos makes it easy to connect any
185 IoT device.
- 186 • ICOS system is an open repository of solutions for SCs, offering a set
187 of existing applications and projects that can be reused for application
188 creation.

189 *2.3. Deficiencies detected in current Smart City platforms*

190 Although a lot of research is being done on Smart Cities, there is still a
191 need for a compact system that would be more efficient and scalable. None of
192 the existing Smart City platforms perform a comprehensive Big Data analysis
193 that would consider the wide range of aspects of a city. Thus, we have found
194 a research gap in the literature and propose a novel architecture capable
195 of reusing the functionalities of existing applications. This enables different
196 applications to offer the same functionalities within the same city or in other
197 cities. As a result, the development process is simplified and less time is
198 required to launch a new service and provide it to citizens.

199 As has been observed in the detailed study of the platforms for application
200 development and implementation, not all platforms provide user-oriented ser-
201 vices so that these applications can be used on different platforms. Similarly,
202 the proposal stands out from the rest of the platforms because it allows de-
203 velopers to use the technologies they know best or those best adapted to the
204 problem they want to solve. So that these technologies can be integrated
205 transparently in the platform.

206 As has been observed in the detailed study of the platforms for application
207 development and implementation, not all platforms are capable of providing
208 user-oriented services. Similarly, the proposal stands out from the rest of
209 the platforms because it allows developers to use the technologies they know
210 best or those best adapted to the problem they want to solve. So that these
211 technologies can be integrated transparently in the platform. The other
212 platforms often do not allow to work in a distributed and modular way.
213 Similarly, the scalability and calculation capacity are also deficiencies that
214 the proposal covers.

215 In addition, one of the main characteristics of Smart Cities is the hetero-
216 geneity of all its components [27], both in the final applications and in the
217 technology used in the deployed infrastructure. For example, within the IoT
218 sector, there are many manufacturers, protocols and communication tech-
219 nologies [28], [29]. As detailed below, one of the main advantages of the
220 platform presented in this paper is that it is compatible with any technology
221 or manufacturer.

222 To achieve this objective, high-performance computing (HPC) is sup-
223 ported by computing technologies such as clusters, supercomputers or paral-
224 lel computing. The majority of current proposals on distributed computing
225 are based on high-performance computing.

226 3. Proposed architecture

227 The main novelty of the article lies in the proposed platform (a scheme
228 is shown in Figure 1), which allows any city to offer a series of applications
229 as services in a simple way. The citizens and the administration personnel
230 of each city are the direct users of these applications.

231 The platform consists of two distinct parts, the communication architec-
232 ture and the deployment architecture. These two parts are described in-depth
233 in separate subsections. Firstly, we focus on the communication architec-
234 ture, which makes it possible for simple nodes to process information in a
235 distributed way. Furthermore, we describe how the central system enables
236 communication between the different elements that form part of the smart
237 city, ensuring adaptation to the size and computing needs of the elements
238 that communicate. The second subsection focuses on the deployment archi-
239 tecture.

240 3.1. *Communication architecture*

241 The development of applications is simplified thanks to the possibility
242 of reusing previously developed components without having to understand
243 their implementation, technology or communication requirements (there are
244 no APIs to be called). In order to reuse the functionality of any previously
245 developed module or to create a new module with a previously developed
246 functionality, it is only necessary to perform a data dump of the application
247 database (of any type: MongoDB, MariaDB, etc.). Then, an answer is gener-
248 ated by the corresponding component and is delivered to the database. It is

Figure 1: Proposed architecture schema showing the three different levels: citizen and administration applications (top), information management block (middle) and developed modules providing the main functionalities.

249 necessary to perform an initial configuration by introducing some simple pa-
 250 rameters in the platform configuration scripts. The components that execute
 251 the requests of each application in the platform are based on a mechanism
 252 called Kafka, Kafka Connect and Apache Arrow. The architecture also inte-
 253 grates a rules engine (JESS). JESS facilitates the definition of rules which
 254 are executed once the conditions defined by the users are met. These tools
 255 allow to send formatted data in real-time.

256 The information is exchanged with the developer in a transparent man-
 257 ner by means of Kafka topics. More specifically, a topic is used to send
 258 the input information to each of the developed modules (Development input
 259 topics in the Figure 1). As many topics as needed are sent to communicate
 260 with the applications that require a certain functionality (Development-App
 261 output topics in the Figure 1). These topics are configured through two
 262 bash scripts (included in the modules “App connector” and “Development

263 connector” of Figure 1). Kafka connectors have been implemented to per-
 264 form this exchange, which are in charge of transferring the information from
 265 databases to topics and from topics to databases. In addition, Apache Ar-
 266 row is used as an auxiliary technology, which makes it possible to convert
 267 binary data, speeding up both the information transfer and the data parsing
 268 process. The platform runs in a fully distributed manner and can use differ-
 269 ent existing cloud environments, both externally (Azure, Amazon, etc.) and
 270 locally/privately managed.

Figure 2: Mechanism for the automatic exchange of information.

271 Model of communication between an app and a development through
 272 Kafka and Kafka Connect (see Figure 2). Two topics (Kafka) are used for
 273 this purpose: Application1 input topic: where input information for App1 is
 274 dumped. Application1 client1 output topic: where the content of the appli-
 275 cation1 output is dumped. There are four Kafka connectors, of two types: 1)
 276 source connectors: they return information from the database to the topic;
 277 2) sink connectors: they dump information from the topic to the database.
 278 Finally, it should be noted that in Application1input topic, the inputs (for
 279 Application1) of all the Developments are dumped. And a new output topic
 280 is created for each new development (Application1 Development1 output
 281 topic) so that the respective connectors can perform the data transfer.

282 The collection of data through the use of sensors has been a crucial aspect
 283 of the architecture design because it enables HPC. Since the architecture is
 284 modular and performs big data analysis, it must be capable of acquiring data
 285 from very diverse sources (crawlers, social networks, other applications and
 286 sensors). The sensors the architecture uses are KNX as middleware. KNX fa-
 287 cilitates simple virtualization. In this way, intelligent embedded automatisms

288 can be created. Virtualization blurs the connection between hardware and
289 software by allowing multiple operating systems to run on a single processor.
290 This enables the aggregation of computing power to solve complex energy
291 optimization problems in Intelligent Buildings or Smart Cities. Agent-based
292 architectures enable complex data analysis through distributed computing
293 [30] [31]. In addition, these architectures allow to incorporate calculation
294 capacity in individual agents through the use of the GPU calculation power
295 of the device in which it is running (an agent or a group of agents can be
296 deployed in different devices).

297 *3.2. Deployment architecture*

298 To support the central system in which the Kafka environment is deployed
299 in a distributed mode, it is necessary to calculate the number of nodes that
300 is needed to correctly perform the processing. This allows to adapt the use
301 of resources to the size of the city. In addition, the nodes deployed optimally,
302 in accordance with the consumption predicted for any given moment, as
303 described in the study in [32].

304 To determine the number of nodes that a city needs at each instant, it is
305 necessary to compute a prediction for an instant of time t , that follows the
306 current moment. The length of this instant depends on the booting period
307 (bp) of the servers in which the system is deployed. To design a forecasting
308 system it is important to consider both, the citizens' usual behaviour and
309 any changes that may occur (such as festivities in the city). Given that the
310 prediction approach must be both static and dynamic, the solution is based
311 on a hybrid prediction system.

312 The static part of the prediction system is in charge of estimating the
313 number of future predictions on the basis of historical request patterns. Ac-
314 cording to the estimate, the required number of nodes is deployed. It re-
315 sponds to requests in less than s seconds (the restriction we have set in this
316 case is two seconds). The prediction system implements the static approach,
317 thanks to an SVR that detects patterns according to different inputs, such as:
318 weekday, day time, month, holiday period, number of active users, number
319 of deployed applications, current value, previous value.

320 The dynamic approach is in charge of re-adjusting the system in the event
321 of an increased number of predictions. The static part of the prediction sys-
322 tem is not capable of detecting the increase in requests/messages. Thus,
323 the dynamic part of the prediction system is based on the Poisson distribu-
324 tion [33], which predicts the number of requests/messages according to the

325 queuing theory. Thus, different Poisson distribution formulas are applied to
326 predict the number of requests/messages within a confidence interval.

$$P(k, \lambda) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^k}{k!} = P(X = x) \quad (1)$$

327 where λ ($\lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda > 0$), is the mean number of requests/messages for
328 every interval, k is the number of requests/messages and e represents the
329 Euler's number. $P(k, \lambda)$ is the result of the equations, that is, the probability
330 of receiving k ($k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$) requests/messages.

331 The amount of nodes to be deployed in each period $n * bp$ (where $n =$
332 $1, 2, 3, \dots$ and bp is the "booting period" of each node) must be estimated. For
333 this reason, the prediction system is executed to calculate the number of
334 nodes needed in the interval $n * bp + bp$ to $n * bp + 2 * bp$. The SVR and the
335 Poisson predictor need input information to be able to estimate the required
336 number of nodes. This input information is obtained by the system.

337 The two parts of the node number prediction system are detailed below:

338 3.2.1. Static approach

339 The static prediction system is based on an SVR (Support Vector Re-
340 gression) [34], which predicts the number of requests/messages (that is used
341 to calculate the number of nodes to deploy) considering the patterns found
342 in previous precedents, which are mainly associated with the habits of the
343 platform's users.

344 This SVR predictor considers the following inputs:

- 345 • Weekday: the day of the week (1-7).
- 346 • Daytime: the time of the day in seconds (0-86400).
- 347 • Month: the month of the year (1-12).
- 348 • Public holiday: this parameter indicates if "today" is a working day or
349 not (0,1).
- 350 • Amount of active users on the city platform.
- 351 • Amount of the applications deployed in the system for that city.
- 352 • Amount of requests/messages in t .
- 353 • Amount of requests/messages in $t - 1$.

354 This part of the system follows the static approach, it predicts the number
 355 of requests/messages that will be received at a selected time instant (req_R)
 356 and the predicted number is used as output. The two solutions given by the
 357 static and the dynamic approaches are then used to calculate the number of
 358 nodes to be deployed to respond to those requests/messages, even when they
 359 reach their highest number (this aspect will be described further on).

360 3.2.2. Dynamic approach

361 The following equations have been defined to describe the dynamic ap-
 362 proach:

$$CDF = P(X \leq k) = e^{-\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{\lfloor k \rfloor} \frac{\lambda^i}{i!} = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor k \rfloor} P(k, \lambda) = P_{AC}(k, \lambda) = prob \quad (2)$$

363 where $prob \in [0, 1]$
 364 equation (2) is used to calculate the cumulative probability of the k num-
 365 ber of requests/messages.

$$CDF^{-1} = \max\{k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} : P_{AC}(k, \lambda) \leq prob\} = P_{AC}^{-1}(prob, \lambda) \quad (3)$$

366 equation (3) represents the quantile function for the Poisson distribu-
 367 tion (or inverse cumulative probability), that provides the number of re-
 368 quests/messages up to the cumulative probability as a percentage.

$$CDF^{-1} = k = X_U = P^{-1}(X \leq k) \quad (4)$$

$$probError = 1 - prob \quad (5)$$

369 The value of $probError$, represented in equation (5), is based on the
 370 margin of confidence.

$$RPC = RPN - (X_U - (X_U \bmod RPN)RPN) \quad (6)$$

371 RPC is the “Remaining Processing Capacity” and it is calculated as
 372 defined in equation (6). It represents the number of requests/messages X_U
 373 that can still be attended by the deployed nodes. The variable RPN is
 374 the number of requests per node, which represents the highest number of

375 requests/messages that every node (all of them have the same features) can
 376 manage to process in less than two seconds.

$$LIM_U = CDF^{-1}(prob, \lambda) + RPC - \lambda \quad (7)$$

377 The parameter LIM_U calculated in equation (7) represents the increase
 378 of the amount of requests/messages that can be managed by the nodes,
 379 calculated by the dynamic component.

$$GR(t) = \{x : x = req(t) - req(t - 1)\} \quad (8)$$

380 $GR(t)$ in equation (8) represents the request/message increase rate.

$$GR_{+1}(t) = \{x : x = req(t) - req(t - 2)\} \quad (9)$$

381 $GR_{+1}(t)$ is the growth rate of the request/message that is calculated using
 382 $t - 2$, to determine the limit for the dynamic component, as represented in
 383 equation (9).

$$Ov(x, y) = \sum_{t=x}^y |LIM_U(t) - GR(t)| \quad (10)$$

384 The parameter $Ov(x, y)$ calculated in equation (10) represents the over-
 385 load in an interval between the instants x and y , in other words, the increase
 386 in the amount of requests/messages goes beyond the capacity of the dynamic
 387 part with a fixed confidence interval, $prob$.

388 Figure 3 shows the Poisson probability distribution and Figure 4 shows
 389 the prediction built on this distribution. In the Poisson distribution figure,
 390 each point represents the possibility of receiving a specific amount of re-
 391 quests/messages in discrete distribution. The Poisson distribution depends
 392 on λ (as defined in equation (1)), that is determined considering the values
 393 requested in the time window w_n . The value X_U is obtained as defined in
 394 equation (4) on the basis of a confidence or error interval, as shown in equa-
 395 tion (5). X_U represents the maximum amount of requests/messages that can
 396 be predicted within the confidence interval.

397 In Figure 4, the points represent the number of requests/messages re-
 398 ceived until the current moment. As explained previously, the booting period
 399 is represented by bp and it refers to the time needed to deploy a node. It must
 400 be noted that the result of a prediction obtained in an instant t , is used for
 401 the instant $t + bp$. Rectangles whose border is a continuous line represent the

Figure 3: Dynamic approach behavior - requests/messages vs probability

402 amount of nodes that have already been deployed, and the rectangles whose
 403 border is a dashed line indicate that the nodes have been predicted depend-
 404 ing on the values of the variable X_U . Variable X_L represents the minimum
 405 amount of requests/messages predicted with the given probability.

406 The inverse cumulative probability is then estimated over an established
 407 confidence interval (in our case the value chosen is 95%), the amount of
 408 requests/messages whose probabilities are below that amount is assumed to
 409 be the total number of requests/messages handled by the system.

410 Once the number of requests/messages is estimated by the two approaches,
 411 the system proceeds to calculate the required nodes to provide the result to
 412 those requests/messages.

413 3.2.3. Number of nodes to deploy

414 To determine the amount of nodes that needs to be deployed to attend
 415 all the requests/messages, the predictions provided by the SVR predictor
 416 and the Poisson predictor are taken into account. Given that the system's
 417 priority is to ensure all the requests are replied to in under two seconds, the
 418 amount of nodes to be deployed is calculated as shown in equation (11).

419 After the combination of the two approaches (static and dynamic), the
 420 amount of nodes to deploy is calculated using the higher of the two predicted
 421 values. This solution encourages the assurance that requests/messages are
 422 handled and processed to the detriment of saving on the cost of processing
 423 capacity.

Figure 4: Dynamic approach behavior - time vs requests/messages and nodes to deploy

$$n = \left\lceil \frac{\max(req_R, req_P)}{RPN} \right\rceil \quad (11)$$

424 where n represents the predicted amount of nodes to deploy at the mo-
 425 ment $t + bp$, the variable req_R represents the amount of requests/messages
 426 predicted by the static approach (SVR), the variable req_P is the number of
 427 requests predicted by the dynamic approach, and finally, $requestsPerNode$
 428 is the highest amount of requests/messages that every single node can serve,
 429 ensuring that the response is dispatched in less than two seconds.

430 3.2.4. Node deployment system evaluation

431 Figure 5 presents two charts: i) the upper one shows the number of
 432 requests/messages is represented as circles, the X_U predictions as triangles
 433 and the number of nodes predicted like rectangles; ii) the lower graphic shows
 434 the growth rate+1 following the equation (9) as diamonds. The squares
 435 represent the LIM_U as shown in equation (7), that is also the distance shown
 436 in the upper graphic.

437 It is important to notice that when a diamond is over a rectangle it means
 438 that the number of deployed nodes is not enough to satisfy the two seconds
 439 restriction. In this way, we have a measure of the system performance because
 440 when there is overload respect to the restriction the system begins to recover
 441 as soon as the growth of petitions is below the limit. So the overload of the
 442 system can be calculated as defined in the equation (10).

Figure 5: Representation of the dynamic system limits

443 In this case, despite not being able to satisfy the condition of dispatching
 444 all requests/messages in less than two seconds as marked as restriction, the
 445 designed system guarantees that all requests are dealt with in due order even
 446 though there are overload points that imply that the result is available later
 447 than the established two seconds.

448 One of the main advantages of the proposed system is that the system
 449 can support a volume adapted to the needs, without the need to have a static
 450 upper limit. In all the tests carried out, the upper limit has been marked by
 451 the limitations of the hardware available to support, not having found any
 452 restrictions of the system in terms of scalability beyond the availability of
 453 hardware resources.

454 **4. Results: Two citizen-oriented case studies**

455 In this section, we describe the two case studies that have been conducted
456 to verify the performance of the proposed platform. In particular, the case
457 studies were designed to test the “Smart home platform” and the “Infor-
458 mation analysis platform”, as illustrated in Figure 1. Moreover, we have
459 developed more applications in other fields (such as industry 4.0, city inci-
460 dent management, etc.) to validate the smooth performance and scalability
461 of the platform.

462 *4.1. Smart home platform*

463 In this case study we describe a new IoT platform for improved energy
464 efficiency in homes. This platform has also been tested in multiple industrial
465 environments as an Industrial IoT (IIoT) solution, although, due to data
466 privacy reasons and similarity to the IoT scenario, no specific cases of IIoT
467 have been described.

468 Thanks to the developed smart home platform, unlimited installations
469 can be deployed in homes with a limitless number of sensors that collect a
470 range of data, including: the status of the doors and windows, temperature
471 and humidity of each room, real-time power consumption or presence in each
472 of the rooms. The sensors can follow different protocols, such as Z-wave,
473 M-Bus, DALI, BACnet or Wi-bee over KNX. Several algorithms that use
474 Jade-developed smart agents, are applied to the collected information [35].
475 Those agents use a set of rules and inferences to recommend changes in the
476 energy consumption habits of the inhabitants of a home. The main objective
477 is to reduce energy consumption with all that this entails.

478 The application allows the user to monitor the state of their home in
479 real time, receive notifications, suggestions and define their preferences to
480 optimize energy consumption according to their comfort criteria.

481 The system also obtains information from the Internet about energy prices
482 and tariffs available for the location, as well as information about the user’s
483 behaviour (only if they approve of this kind of information being collected).
484 On the basis of the retrieved information, the rules engine is fed to make
485 new suggestions to the user, such as changing the behaviour of users in
486 the domestic environment or changing the electricity tariff. Suggestions for
487 change of behavior may include doing household chores at times when the
488 price of energy is the lowest. This is achieved through the use of the “Internet

Figure 6: Monitoring the status of a smart home by means of the “Smart home platform” application.

489 information recovery module”, which is also used in the case study presented
 490 below.

491 In this case study, a model designed by the BISITE research group has
 492 been used. The model simulates the activity of a smart city so it can be used
 493 in related case studies. different case studies related to , such as case studies
 494 on energy optimisation in homes or buildings, case studies on transport or
 495 on the energy grid or on the sustainability of cities, Figure 7. In this specific
 496 case, only the residential area has been used, which is the upper central zone
 497 marked in the image.

498 The present case study, Figure 8 has proven that data management is
 499 made possible by the architecture since it simulates the different patterns of
 500 behavior. In this way, it is possible to verify if an optimization of the energy
 501 takes place in the city or not.

502 The Automatic Lighting Management Module (ALMM) using the devel-
 503 oped IoT platform has made it possible to simulate lighting management in
 504 60 homes using the previously presented model. The lighting in 30 of the 60
 505 homes was managed automatically when the system detected that the light
 506 intensity was lower than 200Lux, so that the inhabitants of this house had
 507 sufficient light to carry out their daily tasks. In the other 30 dwellings, the
 508 lighting was managed according to real behaviour (homes of the members
 509 of the BISITE Research Group who have volunteered to replicate the daily
 510 lighting patterns in their homes).

511 The use of this platform has allowed for an easy and fast integration of
 512 the application for intelligent lighting management and has made it possible

Figure 7: BISITE Research Group Mock-Up to simulate transport and energy case studies.

513 to evaluate its effectiveness in 30 homes. The results of the simulation are
514 shown below, grouping the dwellings into three groups of ten dwellings each
515 (Average consumption). As can be seen in the table 1 there is a reduction
516 in the three groups with respect to the same period if they had not used the
517 ALMM with an average percentage of 27%.

518 As shown in Table 2, the energy consumption is notably lower in the case
519 study. We can see how the p -value is always under 0.05, which ensures the
520 effectiveness of ALMM and the platform in integrating various management
521 modules into Smart Cities or intelligent buildings.

522 *4.2. Information analysis platform*

523 This case study has used all the publicly available information on the
524 Internet about users. This type of analysis can be very useful in applications
525 such as terrorist searches, analysis of suspect profiles, etc. The system creates
526 a series of crawlers that retrieve public data from all pages that fulfill the
527 criteria specified in the input form shown in Figure 9. Only two prior fields

(a) Automatic lighting management through the platform of 30 homes.

(b) Automatic lighting management through the platform of 25 homes.

(c) Automatic lighting management through the platform of 20 homes.

(d) Automatic lighting management through the platform of 15 homes.

Figure 8: Different stages of consumption simulation in intelligent buildings of the mock-up.

Table 1: Results of energy consumption in the different steps of the experiment.

	Baseline Period (kWh)	Simulation Period (kWh)	Difference (kWh)	Savings (%)
1 st gr.	19.71	14.24	5.47	-27,75
2 nd gr.	18.66	13.65	5.01	-26.84
3 rd gr.	16.68	12.24	4.44	-26.61

Table 2: Result of the Student’s t-test and Levene’s test performed to assess the difference of means and variances between the Baseline data and the Evaluation period for the three groups.

	Baseline Period		Evaluation Period					
	Mean (kWh)	Std. Deviation (kWh)	Mean (kWh)	Std. Deviation (kWh)	t	Sig. (2-Tailed)	F	Sig.
1 st gr.	19.71	2.40	14.24	5.16	5.25	0.000	9.42	0.003
2 nd gr.	18.66	2.09	13.65	4.63	5.39	0.000	10.19	0.002
3 rd gr.	16.68	2.41	12.24	4.22	5.00	0.000	7.73	0.007

528 are required, which are the first and last name, and the system is responsible
 529 for retrieving all the existing data.

The image shows a web interface for a 'DATA ANALYSIS DASHBOARD'. At the top, there is a dark blue header with the text 'DATA ANALYSIS DASHBOARD'. Below this, there are two main sections. The first section, titled 'Analysis Choices', contains a 'Username' input field, a blue button labeled 'TWEETS ANALYSIS', a blue button labeled 'WEB SEARCH', and a 'Keywords' input field with a green button labeled 'START STREAM'. The second section, titled 'Personal Information', contains several input fields: 'First Name', 'First Surname', 'Last Surname', 'Email #1', 'Email #2', 'Phone Number #1', 'Phone Number #2', and 'Keywords'. Below these fields is a dropdown menu and a row of social media icons (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.). At the bottom of this section is a blue button labeled 'LAUNCH WEB SEARCH'.

Figure 9: Input form shown in the frontend of the “Information analysis platform” application.

530 Once all the data has been downloaded, a series of studies are carried
 531 out on the sources from which they have been retrieved, the information and
 532 the images they contained. As a result, it is possible to create a set of clusters
 533 that classify the results into possible identities. For example, hundreds
 534 of people called ‘John Doe’ can be found and the system is able to classify
 535 them according to the analyzed results. From each cluster, we obtain their

	Max. allowed devices	Data transference
Azure IoT Hub [38]	500	8,000 messages/day
AWS IoT [39]	No limit	8,300 messages/day
Watson IoT [40]	500	200 MB/month
Proposed platform	No limit	10,000 messages/second

Table 3: IoT platforms comparison.

536 profiles on social networks, their most relevant images (we analyze the pic-
537 tures in which their faces are visible and compare the faces in different images
538 in existing libraries to check if they are the same person), their addresses,
539 emails, companies with which they are associated, related users, phone num-
540 bers, nationality, etc. At the moment, the system works in Spanish and
541 English, however, since it mainly uses the Stanford NLP development [36],
542 it is adaptable to new languages.

543 Although Kafka has some limitations in the passage of messages, its use to
544 connect IoT devices in the platform proposed for the management of Smart
545 Cities offers certain improvements over existing technologies, as can be seen
546 in Table 3. The data shown in the table have been retrieved from [37].

547 It can be observed in the comparative table that the proposal presented
548 in this work allows for an unlimited connection of devices which is not offered
549 by the rest of the state of the art platforms. In addition, the data transfer is
550 far superior to its strongest competitor AWS IoT, having the ability to send
551 10,000 messages/second. These features are a prerequisite for managing the
552 data produced in a city such as those used in the case study.

553 5. Conclusions and future work

554 A distributed and modular platform has been developed. Thanks to its
555 modularity, it is possible to provide the citizen with a set of applications that
556 reuse functionalities. Not only citizens benefit but also the developers who
557 can use the technologies they know best or those that adapt best to the prob-
558 lem they want to solve. Furthermore, those technologies can be integrated
559 transparently in the platform. The required scalability and computing ca-
560 pacity, as well as other aspects, directly depend on the preferences of the
561 system administrator or on the city’s needs. Nevertheless, the infrastructure
562 that supports the proposed platform is completely transparent for the sys-
563 tem, making it possible to use the module that best adapts to the needs of

564 each city. Despite the great benefits of using Kafka, it also has some limita-
565 tions, especially in large cities. The maximum number of messages that can
566 be handled per second is 100,000. Nevertheless, the system could be scaled
567 for large cities so as to make it capable of dealing with high information traf-
568 fic. Kafka also has a limitation on the number of topics that can be created,
569 which is less than a thousand. However, this does not impede the scalability
570 of the system, because if it is necessary to create more than a thousand topics
571 in a large city, different information transmission systems can be created in
572 a single city using Kafka.

573 Although there are certain limitations due to the use of the selected tech-
574 nology, those limits can be overcome easily. As it has been shown, the archi-
575 tecture has extra computing capacity for the analysis of large amounts
576 of data. Although only two case studies have been conducted, there are
577 currently more than ten functionalities that the different applications can
578 perform almost automatically. We continue working on providing new func-
579 tionalities to meet all the possible needs that may arise in any type of city.
580 One of the use cases on which we are currently working, is the integration
581 of Salamanca's public transport information, which includes buses (15 lines)
582 and bicycles for rent (more than 160). We are working on developing the ap-
583 plications fully, so that they can be offered to end-users. These applications
584 will help improve the quality of life in the city.

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